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Modelling Agricultural Risk Management Policies - The Implementation of the Income Stabilization Tool in Italy

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Abstract

This paper investigates the potential impact of the income stabilisation tool (IST) introduced in the European Common Agricultural Policy to reduce farmers’ income risks using Italian agriculture as case study. The paper extends the existing literature by investigating the effects of two implementation issues: level of aggregation of mutual funds (MF); definition of farmers’ contribution (i.e. premium) to MF. We use a simulation approach based on a FADN panel data set of 3421 farms over a period of 7 years to investigate effects on i) farm-level income variability, ii) the expected level and variability of indemnifications at the level of mutual funds and iii) the distribution of net benefits from this policy instrument across the farm population. We find that the introduction of the IST would lead to a significant reduction of income variability in Italian agriculture. Our results support the establishment of a national mutual fund due to the high volatility of indemnification levels at more disaggregated (e.g. regional or sectoral) levels. In addition, our results propose that farmers’ contribution to mutual funds, i.e. premiums paid, should be modulated according to farm size as this reduces the inequality of the distribution of benefits of such tool within the farm population.

Keywords: income stabilisation tool, policy implementation, mutual funds, risk-management policies.

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1 Introduction

Farming is a risky business because forces beyond the control of farmers affect their income (Mishra and Sandretto, 2002). More specifically, farmers' income reveal a high variability due to volatile product prices and in yields, as well as due to the occurrence of catastrophic risks such as natural disasters and animal/plant diseases. The resulting income instability negatively affects farmers' well-being and their decisions, their ability to expand operations and repay debt and, in turns, this can also have secondary effects on agribusiness firms and creditors (Mishra and El-Osta, 2001; Mishra and Holtausen, 2002; Mishra and Sandretto, 2002; Vrolijk and Poppe, 2008; Vrolijk et al., 2009). Thus, farm income and farm income distribution are of high importance for policy makers (e.g. Severini and Tantari, 2013, El Benni and Finger, 2013, Liesivaara and Myyrä, 2016a and b). Several instruments have been proposed to support farmers in coping with (increasing) income risks (see, e.g. Bielza Diaz-Caneja et al., 2008; Meuwissen et al., 2013; for examples and overviews). Indeed, agricultural policies both in the US and European countries have provided disaster relief by *ad hoc* measures to cover (*ex-post*) catastrophic risks, product price stabilisation policies and direct support (e.g. the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) direct payments) (Severini et al., 2016).

Recent policy developments have been characterised by a shift away from direct public intervention towards the support of public-private partnerships that help farmers to cope with the risks they face. National governments aim to reduce the provision of *ad hoc* measures to cover catastrophic risks because this of the unpredictable nature of the costs of such measures and the growing financial constraints faced in recent years. Recent CAP reforms have reduced the role of price stabilisation measures. Moreover, next CAP reform steps will likely reduce the decoupled support provided by

direct payment policies. All these developments are increasing EU farmers' income risks, which is furthermore expected to be amplified by increasing risk exposure due to climate change (e.g. Reidsma et al., 2010). However, the recent reform of the CAP has introduced three different risk management measures that are based on the developments of public-private partnerships within the framework of the EU Rural Development Policy (RDP)³. First, insurance premium subsidies have been introduced (already 2009, e.g. Liesivaara and Myyrä, 2016b). Second, mutual funds are supported (Meuwissen et al., 2013). Third, the so-called Income Stabilisation Tool (IST) has been introduced (see El Benni et al., 2016, for details).

This latter tool explicitly aims at smoothing the farm income variability between years. Hence, in comparison with yield insurances, it focuses not just on production risk but on the overall farm income offering, at least potentially, large scope for managing income risk.

The IST provides compensation to farmers who experience a severe income drop, i.e. income decreases larger than 30% from the expected income.

The interest of policy-makers for the IST is due to four major reasons. First, farmers protection under the IST focuses on the key variable of interest, i.e. income. This represents the economic wellbeing of a farm household much better than revenues of a single commodity and implicitly accounts for various correlations between prices and yields and across profits of different farm activities (Meuwissen et al., 2003; Severini et al., 2016). Second, IST is in agreement with WTO green-box requirements (e.g. Mary et al., 2013). Third, IST has the potential to cover also systemic risks (specifically price risk) that are not covered by purely commercial insurances hampering the principles of risk pooling (Meuwissen et al., 2003). Fourth, the tools support a public-private partnership because farmers must be organised in mutual funds (MF) and have to cover part of the indemnity costs (i.e. at least 35% of these) as well as management costs incurred by the MF.

³ Regulation (EU) No 1305/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 December 2013 on support for rural development by the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) (OJ L 347, 20.12.2013, p.487).

There is now a large amount of explorative research on the farm-, sector- and country-level effects of IST. This literature focuses on actuarial evaluations of a potential income insurance, its governmental costs, potential beneficiaries within the farm population as well as conceptual studies on problems of adverse selection and moral hazard with such whole-farm income insurance tools (dell'Aquila and Cimino, 2012; Liesivaara et al., 2012; Liesivaara and Myyrä, 2016a; Pigeon et al., 2014; Mary et al., 2013; El Benni et al. 2016; Finger and El Benni, 2014a and 2014b).

This research has shown that the introduction of such tool: i) stabilizes farm-incomes (Finger and El Benni, 2014a), ii) affects the income inequality within the farm population (Finger and El Benni, 2014a), iii) the benefits from such tool might be highly heterogeneous across farm types (El Benni et al. 2016), iv) causes highly volatile levels of indemnification payments, requiring large buffers (Pigeon et al. 2014), v) might cause large transaction costs (Liesivaara et al., 2012), vi) indemnification patterns are highly dependent on the calculation of the reference income (Finger and El Benni, 2014b), vii) might cause moral hazard problems along value chains (Liesivaara and Myyrä, 2016a).

The conducted research, however, remained on conceptual levels, without explicit aspects on implementation issues. This observation is also due to the fact that, despite the potential appeal of this tool, IST has not been implemented yet in EU Member States. Now, however, first countries and regions declared interest in establishing IST: Italy, Hungary and the Spanish region Castilla y León (Bardají and Garrido, 2016). Important steps towards implementation that have not been addressed in empirical research so far are: i) the specification of aspects concerning the structure of mutual funds (MF) across sectors and space and ii) the specification of farmers' contribution to MF. These decisions could affect income stabilizing properties, viability of mutual funds, income inequality in the agricultural sector and the distribution of benefits across space and farm types. These issues have, for instance in Italy, led to a postponement of the implementation of the IST (Trestini and Boatto, 2015; Trestini et al., 2018; ISMEA, 2015).

Opting against a single national mutual fund but focus on specific sectors and/or regions has several advantages. Already existing institutions (e.g. Producer Organizations) could be used to facilitate the establishment of a MF and increase the likelihood of an agreement among farmers. Moreover, such MF would have a more detailed knowledge about the participating farmers and could thus better manage moral hazard problems. Thus, there are substantially lower transaction costs expected for low aggregation levels. Finally, such disaggregation implies a limited redistribution of benefits (as well as costs) of the policy among different sectors and regions, which is an important aspect for the acceptance of such policy. A potential limitation when MF operate on a specific sector and specific regions, is that it may not be possible to effectively pool risks because the underlying risks are systemic. For example, when only a small region or a specific sector is addressed, all farms may be affected by the systemic weather risk or the same market risk. Under these circumstances, this causes large indemnification events within a MF, requires large buffers and/or re-insurance, which increases costs.

Another important issue is how farmers should pay the contributions, i.e. premiums, to the MF. Farms might contribute to the IST using flat-rate premium levels (Finger and El Benni, 2016), or contribute according to income or risk levels. The choice on farmers' contribution will have implications for the costs and risk reducing effects of the IST.

We illustrate the effects of the specification of MF and farmers' contributions on the variability of farm income and the distribution of benefits of IST among the farm population using the example of Italian agriculture in a unique empirical analysis. Thus, we contribute an empirical analysis that feeds directly into ongoing policy debates in Italy on the implementation of the IST. Moreover, shedding light into these implementation aspects constitutes an important basis for policy decisions also in other countries.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 describes methodology and data. Section 3 presents the results of the analysis. The final section 4 concludes and draws some policy implications.

2 Methodology

In our analysis, we use bookkeeping (i.e. farm accountancy data network, FADN) data for the entire Italian agricultural sector across a large set of farms and years that allows us to draw conclusions for the farm population at large and to investigate a large set of farm and farmers' characteristics that may influence the effects of the IST (e.g. Finger and El Benni 2014a). The methodology section first introduces the general framework of the IST; secondly presents the employed scenarios and thirdly addresses the assessment of the outcomes based on income variability and distributions of benefits.

2.1 General framework of the IST.

As in previous analyses, we assume participation in the IST to be mandatory (EC, 2009; Liesivaara et al., 2012; Finger and El Benni, 2014a and 2014b; El Benni et al., 2016). Following the EU regulation, a farmer is indemnified if his/her income drops more than 30 per cent compared with the expected income level. For the i -th individual farm:

I_{it} is the realised income at the t -th year

E_{it} is the expected income at the t -th year and it is assumed to be the average of the realised incomes of the previous three years (see Finger and El Benni (2014b) for discussions) as:

$$E_{it} = \frac{1}{3} \sum_{t-4}^{t-1} I_{it}$$

I_{Rit} is the reference income at the t-th year and it is calculated as: $I_{Rit} = \alpha \cdot E_{it}$ where α is equal to 0.7.

The indemnity paid in the t-th year for the i-th farm is:

$$Ind_{it} = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } I_i \geq I_{Rit} \\ \beta \cdot (E_{it} - I_i) & \text{if } I_i < I_{Rit} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where β is equal to 0.7. This partial compensation is supposed to further reduce moral hazard effects of the IST.

2.2 *Scenarios of the specification of the IST.*

Specification of the Mutual Funds. Simulations are developed regarding the level of aggregation of the MF. In particular, it has been considered the case of: a) a single national-wide MF; b) MFs working on the 3 altimetry regions of Italy (Mountain, hill, plain); c) MFs working on 5 macro-regions of Italy (i.e. North-West, North-East, Centre, South, Islands); d) MFs working on 7 specific sectors (i.e. farms specialised in: fieldcrops; horticulture; permanent crops; grazing livestock; granivore livestock; mixed crop farms; mixed livestock, crops and livestock farms).

Considering different specifications of the MFs is important because different regions and types of farming face different risk profiles. For example, in the north of Italy, production risk due to hail is substantially higher than in the other regions. Furthermore, farms belonging to the considered regions generally differ in terms of structural characteristics and production orientation. For example, farms in the plains are larger than those in the other altimetry regions. Finally, farms belonging to the same type of farming face very similar market risks. Thus, mutual funds tailored to specific regions and types of farming are expected to face some systemic risks, which would imply large fluctuations of the paid indemnities over time.

Specification of contribution of farmers to the MF. The impact of the IST is assessed under two different assumptions:

- a) IST is fully subsidised by the government (i.e. farmers do not pay neither indemnities, nor management costs of the MF)
- b) Farmers pay contributions that are set to recover 35% of the indemnities paid by the MF⁴.

The total indemnification paid by the MF in year t ($TInd_t$) is thus derived by means of a weighted sum of farm level indemnities:

$$TInd_t = \sum_{i=1}^n Ind_{it} \cdot w_i \quad (2)$$

where w_i are the statistical weights attached to each FADN farm (Indexed by i). These weights indicate how many similar farms can be found in the total population (EC, 2010) and are used to extrapolating the results to the entire country and to groups of farms⁵.

Farm level contributions are calculated in two alternative ways. First, a flat rate contribution is chosen that represents premium calculation, for example, in the catastrophic crop insurance program in the USA (e.g. Shields, 2015). As in Finger and El Benni (2014a), we simply divide the 35% of the total indemnification paid by the MF in each of the years by the sum of the weights of the sampled farms.

$$ContF_t = 0.35 \cdot TInd_t / \sum_{i=1}^n w_i \quad (3)$$

$ContF_t$ is the flat rate contribution to be paid by the farmers to the MF. In this way, each farm pays exactly the same contribution in a specific year regardless its size and the probability to receive an indemnification.

Moreover, we also calculate a farm-specific contribution by distributing the total indemnification paid by the MF proportionally to the expected income of each farm as it follows:

⁴ The EU regulation allows to cover up to 65% of the paid indemnities by public funds.

⁵ Criteria that define similarity include region, type of farm and economic size class (EC, 2010).

$$ContE_{it} = (0.35 \cdot TInd_t / TE_t) \cdot E_{it} \quad (4)$$

$ContE_{it}$ is for the contribution paid by each farmer in each year, and E_{it} is expected income of farm i in year t . In this case, the contribution differs among farms even in the same year.

2.3 Assessment of the effects of IST and test strategies

Frequency and level of indemnification

The relative frequency of indemnification can be represented by mean of the ratio of farms receiving indemnification over the total number of farms. The relative extent of the indemnities paid can be expressed as an indemnity rate. This is the ratio of total paid indemnity over total expected income ($TInd_t / TE_t$) where TE_t is the weighted sum of the expected income of all farms of the sample. The indemnity rate can be calculated also for specific groups of farms.

In order to conduct pairwise comparisons among the considered farm groups and configurations of MF, we used non-parametric bootstrap to derive confidence intervals. Following Payton et al. (2003), non-overlapping 83% confidence intervals can be used as indication for the rejection of the hypothesis of identical values in both groups at the 5% level of significance.

Variability of farm income over time

The analysis relies on 4 different income indicators (for each farm and year, indexes are omitted).

I observed income (i.e. without IST)

$$I_I = I + Ind \quad (5)$$

$$I_{IF} = I - ContF \quad (6)$$

$$I_{IE} = I_I - ContE \quad (7)$$

The last three indicators refer to the application of the IST but under different rules. I_I includes the received indemnification but does not subtract farmers' contribution to the MF. This is an hypothetical situation in which the policy covers all costs of the IST.

On the contrary, indicators I_{IF} and I_{IE} include the received indemnifications (as I_I) but are net of the farmers' contribution to the MF. This latter is paid according to the two considered criteria (Index F refers to $ContF$ while index E refers to $ContE$) but both allow the recovery of 35% of the whole amount of the indemnities paid.

Income variability has been assessed by calculating the standard deviation (SD), the Median Absolute Deviation (from the median) (MAD), a more robust measure for dispersion, and Coefficient of Variation (CV) over the years 2011-2014 for each farm. Comparing the income variability of the 4 considered income indicators allows to assess the potential income stabilizing effect of the IST under different implementation rules. To this end we compare CVs using non-parametric Wilcoxon tests (Wilcoxon, 1945).f

Distribution of the financial net benefits of the IST among farms.

The distribution of the cost and benefits of the IST has been assessed only under the assumption that farmers pay contributions. This has been done by using the ratio between average indemnities received and the average contribution paid (over the considered four-year period) for each farm:

$$DCB_i = \frac{Avg(Ind)_i}{Avg(Cont)_i} \quad (7)$$

This ratio, that is zero for farms that have not received any indemnity, represents the financial benefit/cost ratio related to the IST⁶. Analysing the distribution of this indicator within the considered farms allows to assess the extent of the redistribution of the net benefits of the policy. An uneven distribution of this indicator suggests that a relatively large number of farms do not benefit from this policy while other farms enjoy a relatively high level of net benefits. This piece of information is important in the design of the policy because policy-makers are generally interested on how policy benefits are distributed among the population.

3 Data

Our analysis is based on a balanced sample of 3421 farms belonging to the Italian FADN consecutively in the year from 2008 to 2014 and not having negative average income⁷. The focus is on the Farm Net Value Added that measures the amount available for remuneration of the fixed production factors (work, land and capital) (EC, 2010). This indicator has been adopted by the European Commission and several analyses related to IST because it is the most comparable indicator between Member States and because it does not vary according to the relative importance of family own production factors (EC, 2009; El Benni et al., 2016; Pigeon et al., 2014). Income is measured on a per farm basis. All figures are deflated to allow comparability among data from different years by mean of the Eurostat Harmonised Index of Consumer Prices (HICP)⁸.

4 Results and discussion

⁶ Another important benefit of the IST for risk adverse farmers is the reduction of the down side income risk generated by this tool.

⁷ As in previous analyses, the exclusion of farms with negative average income (i.e. 84 farms over 3505 that is 2.4%) is motivated by the fact that it is not clear how such farmers should be handled and, in particular, how they should pay the contribution to the MF (Finger and El Benni, 2014a).

⁸ Available at: <http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/hicp/data/database>. Accessed on March 2017.

3.1 Frequency and expected level of indemnification

We find that around 55% of the represented farms would receive at least one indemnification within the four considered years (Table 2) or around 21% per year in the considered period. This latter figure is higher than the one reported by El Benni et al. (2016) for Swiss agriculture. More 30% of those farms receive only one indemnification and more than 16% exactly two indemnifications within the four years. On the contrary, only a very limited number of farms receive indemnifications in more than two of the considered years (Table 2).

With a single national MF, the overall amount of indemnities paid in the years 2011 – 2014 is around 9% of the expected income (i.e. indemnity rate) (second column of Table 3). Given that this figure refers to the overall represented population, this suggests that the IST could provide a not negligible financial support. However, this level differs among the considered regions and types of farming (Table 3). For example, indemnity rate is relatively high in the hill regions and in the islands of Italy. Differences are also found among farm types: farms specialised in horticulture have a relative level of indemnification higher than the average, while the opposite is true for specialised grazing livestock farms (Table 3). This confirms that different groups of farmers face different levels of income risk.

The variability over time of the relative level of indemnifications (third and fourth column of Table 3) sharply and significantly increases in almost all cases when farms are grouped according to the considered dimensions. In two of the three altimetry regions, CV are significantly higher than the one calculated for the national MF case (Table 3). This is even more emphasized when farms are grouped by macro-regions and TF. Relevant is the case of the Center of Italy where, despite the low expected indemnity rate, this has a very large variability. Within the TFs, the variability is significantly higher in granivore livestock farms as well as the two mixed crops and mixed livestock groups of farms.

These results suggest that MF defined at a lower than national aggregation level can be less viable than a national MF in pooling the risk of all members. This depends on the fact that similar/contiguous farms face the same risks and that MF aggregate a lower number of farms.

However, under this specification, MF could better define the contribution of the farms making it more tailored to the peculiar extent of the income risk each group is facing. Hence, this reduces the extent of the distribution of policy benefits among farms. However, this latter result crucially depends also on how the contribution is calculated.

3.2 Farm contributions to the IST

The flat rate contributions (i.e. each farm of a group pays the same amount in a given year) are around 1400 Euro per farm and year under the assumption of the national MF and a subsidy rate of 65% of the paid indemnities. However, when MF are constructed according to altimetry regions or macro-regions, each group pays a different contribution. This clearly depends on both the expected relative level of indemnification and the size of the sampled farms. Regarding the altimetry regions, premiums would be highest in the plain region. Large differences can also be found among macro-regions with high contributions found in Islands and North-West of Italy. Even larger differences are found among TF with the highest levels in specialised granivore livestock farms.

When contribution is defined according to the average income level, there are large differences in the contribution paid by the farmers. This is true not just for the national MF, but also when the MFs are developed within the considered groups.

These results clearly suggest that the two considered approaches to calculate the contributions differ in terms of distribution of the cost of the IST among farms.

3.3 Impact on income variability

We find the IST to significantly reduce income variability. This is because this tool shifts to the left the distribution of the CV of the income among the considered farm sample (Figure 1) by reducing the frequency of the high levels of income variability.

Implementing the IST under the full subsidisation hypothesis (I_I) allows a reduction of the absolute level of income variability (i.e. SD and MAD) as well as in a significant reduction of the CV level (Table 4). Note that this finding is caused by two components. First, income variability is reduced. Second, the subsidy leads to an increase of mean and median income levels. Thus, our results confirm the findings of Finger and El Benni (2014) that lowering the subsidisation rate reduces the income stabilising effect of the IST.

Moving from the full subsidy scenario to a contribution by farmers, only slightly reduces the income stabilising role of the IST (Figure 1). Under both scenarios how premiums are derived (I_{IF} and I_{IE}), the absolute variability declines in comparison with the observed condition (i.e. without IST). Introducing the IST under the I_{IF} and I_{IE} specifications generates a large reduction of income variability compared to the no IST situation both expressed in absolute terms (i.e. SD and MAD) as well as in terms of relative income variability using the CV (Table 4). Furthermore, the mean and median income levels increase, reflecting that parts of the indemnities are recovered by means of the farmers' contributions.

However, the way farmers pay the contribution to MF can affect this result. When the contribution is proportional to the expected income (I_{IE}), the median CV declines slightly more than in the case of the flat-rate contribution (I_{IF}) (Table 4 and Figure 1). Hence, the way the contribution system is designed has implications on the income stabilising effect of the IST even considering exactly the same design of the indemnification mechanism. More specifically, the proportional contribution approach is found to be very effective to reduce income variability.

The income stabilizing role of the IST does not change according to how the MF are designed when the whole sample is considered (Table 5). However, this is not the case when specific sub-groups of farms are considered. For example, with flat rate contributions, the IST reduces the income variability of mountain farms stronger than that of farmers located in the hills (fourth column of Table 5). Similarly, when farmers pay a contribution proportional to their expected income (fifth column of Table 5), farmers located in the Islands experience a drop in variability from the baseline situation that is substantially higher than in the case of those located in the Center of Italy.

3.4 Distribution of the net financial benefits of the IST

The way contributions are calculated, strongly affects the distribution of the net financial benefit of the policy. Figure 2 shows the very different distribution of net gains from the IST under the two considered approaches used to calculate farmers' contributions to MF (i.e. flat and proportional rate).

In both cases, 1577 farms of the whole sample (3421) do not receive any indemnity in the four considered years (dotted yellow line in Figure 2). Thus, we observe a strong transfer component from farms with low income variability, receiving no indemnification under the IST, to indemnified farms. Yet, even several farms receiving indemnities have a negative net benefit because these indemnities do not compensate for the paid contributions (i.e. Ind/Contr lower than unity as represented by the horizontal dotted line in Figure 2). More specifically, only 1002 farms under the flat rate case have positive net benefits (i.e. Ind/Cont >1), while this number is 1304 under the proportional contribution case (Figure 2). This means that, under this latter case, 302 additional farms enjoy positive net financial benefits if compared with the flat rate case. This results can be explained by the fact that the flat rate contribution allows some farms to benefit of an extraordinary high level of Ind/Cont (i.e. those located on the right side of Figure 2). Thus, our findings confirm the results of El Benni et al. (2016) that flat rate contributions to the IST may generate uneven distributions of benefits of the IST.

4 Conclusions

We find that the income stabilization tool recently introduced in the common agricultural policy would lead to a significant stabilization of farm incomes in Italian agriculture. We provide the first analysis that shows how implementation aspects affect the impact and potential costs of the application of this tool.

We have shown that moving from a national to a regional/sectorial mutual funds (MF) increases the variability of the total indemnities paid by the MF significantly. More specifically, the relative variability of indemnification rates can be up to 5 times higher if moving to smaller aggregation levels of MF. Hence, such MF focusing on specific regions and sectors would face highly volatile levels of indemnification payments, requiring large buffers (Pigeon et al. 2014) and/or reinsurance. This would result in an increase of the costs incurred by the MF and, consequently, charged to farmers. On the contrary, a nation-wide MF seems to face a limited variability of the total amount of indemnifications over time. This implies that public expense for this tool will be also less variable (more stable) over time under this specification of the MF.

We find that the specification of farmers' contribution, i.e. premiums to the IST, affects its income stabilising effect. For flat rate contributions, regional/sector specific MF seem to be more effective than a national MF in terms of income risk reduction. However, this is not the case when contributions are paid according to their expected income. The level of the contributions farmers pay affects the income stabilising effect of the IST. Lowering the subsidisation rate reduces the income stabilising effect of the IST. However, our results show that also the way farmers pay is important in this regard: a flat rate approach seems less effective than a contribution proportional to the average farm income level in terms of income stabilisation.

The way contributions are designed has relevant implications on how the financial benefits of the policy are distributed among the farm population. For instance, we find that a flat rate contribution generates a very uneven distribution of these benefits across farms. However, this phenomenon is strongly reduced when a proportional contribution is used.

These results support some policy implications. First, developing MF with a high level of aggregation (e.g. national level) may be desirable to avoid highly volatile levels of the total paid indemnifications. Second, this will not reduce the effectiveness of the IST as income stabilising tool. Of course, this kind of design of the IST might cause large transaction costs. Hence, this trade-off should be carefully considered when designing the MF. Third, it seems very appropriate to modulate farmers' contributions to the MF according to farm size avoiding simpler approaches such as flat rate contributions. This modulation decreases the inequality of the distribution of financial benefits of the policy within the farm population and improves the risk reducing effects of the IST.

Finally, the analysis has not considered some other aspects of important policy relevance that should be explored in future analyses on the IST. These include, among others, the potential implications of the application of the IST on the income inequality within the farm population (Finger and El Benni, 2014a) and the factors affecting the distribution of the benefits derived by this tool (El Benni et al. 2016).

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Table 1. Sampled and represented farms. Number of observations and frequency (%).

	Sampled farms		Represented farms	
	N. of obs.s	Freq.	N. of obs.s	Freq.
All observations	3421	100.0%	186191	100.0%
Altimetry regions:				
Mountain	709	20.7%	30806	16.5%
Hill	1458	42.6%	78154	42.0%
Plain	1254	36.7%	77231	41.5%
Macro-regions (MR):				
Center	383	11.2%	14612	7.8%
Islands	194	5.7%	18583	10.0%
South	760	22.2%	50020	26.9%
North-West	1251	36.6%	49647	26.7%
North-East	833	24.3%	53329	28.6%
Types of farming (TF)				
Specialised fieldcrops	844	24.7%	47142	25.3%
Specialised horticulture	305	8.9%	12392	6.7%
Specialised permanent crops	1012	29.6%	75824	40.7%
Specialised grazing livestock	770	22.5%	30975	16.6%
Specialised granivore livestock	98	2.9%	1848	1.0%
Mixed crops	201	5.9%	9529	5.1%
Mixed livestock, crops and livestock	191	5.6%	8481	4.6%

Source: Own elaboration on the Italian FADN sample.

Table 2. Beneficiaries of indemnities over the four considered years (2011 – 2014) in the whole sample of farms. Shares of represented farms (%).

Not indemnified	Indemnified farms				
	At least in one year	of which:			
		1 year	2 years	3 years	4 years
44.8%	55.2%	31.8%	16.6%	6.1%	0.7%

Source: Own elaboration on a constant sample of farms of the Italian FADN.

Table 3. Variability of indemnity rates (Total indemnities paid over expected income - %) in the period 2011 – 2014 according to different configurations of the MF[^].

	Mean	Standard Deviation (SD)	Coefficient of Variation (SD/Mean):	
			CV ^{^^}	Confidence Intervals 8.5 – 91.5%
National MF	9.3%	0.7%	0.079	0.078-0.081
MF by altimetry regions:				
Mountain	8.2%	1.0%	0.121	0.117-0.124
Hill	10.7%	0.5%	0.048	0.047-0.049
Plain	8.7%	1.2%	0.135	0.135-0.139
MF by macro-regions (MR):				
Center	7.8%	3.3%	0.388	0.373-0.392
Islands	14.5%	3.1%	0.223	0.221-0.229
South	8.6%	0.8%	0.098	0.096-0.100
North-West	9.7%	1.2%	0.120	0.117-0.121
North-East	8.0%	0.9%	0.106	0.104-0.109
MF by types of farming (TF)				
Specialised fieldcrops	9.3%	1.4%	0.156	0.153-0.158
Specialised horticulture	14.9%	1.9%	0.127	0.125-0.129
Specialised permanent crops	10.0%	0.9%	0.094	0.094-0.097
Specialised grazing livestock	6.3%	1.3%	0.200	0.196-0.202
Specialised granivore livestock	13.2%	6.1%	0.437	0.427-0.444
Mixed crops	8.3%	2.6%	0.327	0.322-0.333
Mixed livestock, crops and livestock	9.1%	2.9%	0.313	0.310-0.321

[^]Values derived by non-parametric bootstrap (n=1000). ^{^^}The distributions of the CV in all groups are statistically different at 1% from that of the National MF according to Wilcoxon test.

Source: Own elaboration on a constant sample of farms of the Italian FADN.

Table 4. Variability of farm income over time under different IST scenarios. Application of the IST at the national level (i.e. Only one MF). Median values.

<u>Central values</u>		<u>Absolute variability</u>		Coefficient of Variation (SD/Mean)[^]	
Mean	Median	Standard Deviation (SD)	Median Absolute Deviation (MAD)		
Observed income (without IST) (I)					
35769	35025	9438	6646	0.271	
Income with indemnities paid by the IST:					
- without any farmers contribution (I_I)					
39132	37750	7736	5168	0.204	***
- with a flat rate contribution per farm (I_{IF})					
36858	35430	7721	5201	0.219	***
- with contributions proportional to expected income (I_{IE})					
38111	36673	7690	5139	0.211	***

[^] Calculated on the single farm CVs. Median CVs with IST are statistically different at 1% according to Wilcoxon test (***).

Source: Own elaboration on a constant sample of farms of the Italian FADN.

Table 5. Median of the CV of the income over time of the sampled farms under different designs of the MF.

	Median values:				Relative changes:		
	With IST:				With IST:		
	Observed:	No contribution	With contribution: [^]		No contribution	With contribution: [^]	
			Flat	Proportional		Flat	Proportional
<i>I</i>	<i>I_I</i>	<i>I_{IF}</i>	<i>I_{IE}</i>	<i>I_I</i>	<i>I_{IF}</i>	<i>I_{IE}</i>	
National MF	0.271	0.204	0.219	0.211	-24.6%	-19.4%	-22.2%
MF by altimetry regions:			0.218	0.211		-19.6%	-22.0%
Mountain	0.268	0.194	0.201	0.201	-27.7%	-25.1%	-25.0%
Hill	0.259	0.205	0.220	0.212	-21.0%	-15.0%	-18.2%
Plain	0.281	0.209	0.224	0.216	-25.7%	-20.4%	-23.1%
MF by macro-regions (MR):			0.218	0.211		-19.6%	-22.1%
Center	0.257	0.192	0.215	0.217	-25.4%	-16.6%	-15.6%
Islands	0.291	0.204	0.222	0.198	-29.6%	-23.5%	-32.0%
South	0.256	0.205	0.215	0.207	-19.7%	-16.1%	-19.0%
North-West	0.286	0.209	0.227	0.210	-27.0%	-20.7%	-26.8%
North-East	0.266	0.200	0.214	0.213	-25.0%	-19.7%	-19.9%
MF by types of farming (TF):			0.219	0.211		-19.4%	-22.2%
Specialised fieldcrops	0.267	0.206	0.219	0.212	-22.9%	-18.2%	-20.5%
Specialised horticulture	0.268	0.202	0.239	0.216	-24.8%	-11.1%	-19.6%
Specialised permanent crops	0.287	0.212	0.226	0.220	-26.3%	-21.3%	-23.3%
Specialised grazing livestock	0.264	0.192	0.205	0.197	-27.6%	-22.5%	-25.6%
Specialised granivore livestock	0.307	0.228	0.272	0.243	-25.7%	-11.5%	-20.8%
Mixed crops	0.289	0.203	0.214	0.209	-29.9%	-26.1%	-27.6%
Mixed livestock, crops and livestock	0.241	0.192	0.219	0.203	-20.1%	-8.8%	-15.5%

[^]Median values of the whole sample under the four configurations of the MF (i.e. figures in bold) are not statistically significant according to Wilcoxon test. This is true for both the flat and the proportional contribution cases.

Source: Own elaboration on a constant sample of farms of the Italian FADN.

Figure 1. Distribution of the coefficient of variations (CV) of income among farms under different IST scenarios. National MF implementation.

Epanechnikov kernel with $n = 512$.

Source: Own elaboration on a constant sample of farms of the Italian FADN.

Figure 2. Distribution of the net financial benefits of the IST among farms in the period 2011-14. National MF.

Note: Ratio indemnities over contribution in the whole sample of farms (Ind/Contr). Flat rate contribution (Cont_F) and contribution proportional to expected income (Cont_E).

Source: Own elaboration on a constant sample of farms of the Italian FADN.